

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v1

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market & Trends Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D4.1 titled as "Collaboration Platform Design and Development-v1" is used to document the architecture of the ToyLabs Core Platform as well as to provide a plan for the integration of the ToyLabs added-value components in the platform.

The deliverable has the nature of a "Demonstrator", therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the developed software platform, the source code of which can be found in the project's GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

The architecture and (if needed) the integration plan presented in D4.1 will be updated throughout the project as the new components will be further developed and integrated at the end of each development circle, resulting to deliverables D4.2, D4.3 and D4.4 and to the release of the stable final version of the Collaboration Platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D4.1 titled as "Collaboration Platform Design and Development-v1" refers to the first version of the Collaboration Platform which has already been released. The present document includes the description of the architecture of the platform, as well as an integration plan defining the steps for integrating the added value components to the core platform.

The deliverable is of "Demonstrator" type, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the actual software platform developed and released. The source code and the relevant documentation can be found in the project's GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D4.1 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the architecture of the Collaboration Platform v1 (Toylabs Core Platform) delivered
- Section 3 includes the plan and the process for the integration of the added-value component
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable, stating the next imminent steps to be executed

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As identified in the DoA, 4.1 is tightly linked to all other WP4 deliverables, as well as to all WP3 Deliverables.

Deliverables D4.2-D.4.4, which refer to the Toylabs integrated platform will be based on the Core Platform architecture described in D4.1 and will follow the integration plan presented.

Deliverables D3.3.-D3.5 referring to the design and development of the added-value components in development circles, will take into account the integration plan presented in order all development tasks to be fully aligned towards building the integrated versions of the Toylabs platform.

2 ToyLabs Core Platform Architecture

2.1 Platform System Architecture

The 1st version of the ToyLabs Platform which includes - the Core Platform without the added value components - has been released by the consortium as defined in the DoA. In the present document, the system architecture of the ToyLabs Core Platform (TCP) is defined, representing the major terms, components and interactions of the core platform which serves as the backbone of the complete ToyLabs Collaboration Platform implementing the methodology developed in the framework of the project. Specifically, the overall structure of the platform is presented here, in terms of the logical grouping of components into separate layers that communicate with each other and with other clients and applications. Layers are concerned with the logical division of components and functionality, and do not take into account the physical location of components.

Under these terms, the ToyLabs Core Platform architecture can be represented in three layers: (a) the Presentation layer, (b) the Business layer and (c) the Data layer. Next, the layered architecture of the platform is being presented as a diagram and the different layers are being explored.

Figure 1: Core Platform Architecture

- The **presentation layer** consists of all the components that implement the interface between the user and the system. A web-based interface has been implemented that presents user-specific dialogs in a browser. There are three presentation components: for visitors, for business users and for the platform administrators respectively.
- The **business layer** consists of components that implement the workflow of the ToyLabs methodology. In this layer interfaces/ connectors to ToyLabs added value components for Augmented Reality and Market and Trend Analysis are included, as well as to the Partner Matching & Negotiation component which although it may operate independently, its interconnection with the TCP is crucial for the efficient operation of the core platform as well.
- The **data layer** refers to the database(s) used for storing all the data required for the operation of the platform. The layer consists of all data-model and data-storage components used in the platform. For scalability reasons most of the components are implemented stateless and depend on input and output data. In practise, all business- and user-related data handled by the ToyLabs Core Platform are stored in one database (TCP database), as shown in the diagram.

In the following sections, the components of all layers are described, in terms of explaining their purpose and naming the interfaces to any other components.

2.2 Presentation Layer

2.2.1 Visitor Frontend

The visitor frontend is the main landing page where any visitor (ie a user who does not have an account in the platform or is not signed-in) lands upon trying to access the ToyLabs portal. As such, this component serves as the main information point to any user regarding ToyLabs and its operation, presenting all necessary information regarding how users can interact with the platform, who is behind that platform and about the overall purpose and functionalities of the platform. Furthermore, the frontend provides details about the products that are already released or are currently under development and marked as public by their owners, in order to allow visitors to seek and identify products of interest, without the need to register.

The visitor frontend is interconnected with the ToyLabs User frontend in order to both reveal the products and search functions which are available to the user frontend, and also to forward visitors who are interested in becoming members of the ToyLabs ecosystem.

The main data processed in the visitor frontend is the data which is passed to the search function that allows visitors to search over the ToyLabs products lists. Moreover, the visitor frontend processes the initial registration information provided by the user (e.g. his email and password), which is then forwarded to the user platform which performs all the necessary activities for verifying and setting up the user's account in the system.

2.2.2 User Frontend

The user frontend is the main functional screen of ToyLabs that a member of ToyLabs sees once logged into the system with his/her customer account. A main purpose of this frontend is to present the user all necessary information about the activities running in ToyLabs (e.g. products under development, feedback collection etc.) and to provide analytics regarding his/her profile and activities, depending on the type of user. In general, this frontend is used by all the members of the ToyLabs platform in order to create new products, engage in existing product development projects, follow up on existing actions and take part in any activities.

The data processed consists of the user's data as well as of the data of the products created in ToyLabs in which the user is (or can be) engaged in any way. For those products, the platform provides to the user various notifications, tools/ actions to implement as well as useful visualizations and graphs where appropriate.

2.2.3 Admin Panel

The admin panel/ frontend component implements the user interface for the administrators of the platform and for such power users who have the authority to update core functions and data of the platform. After logging in, the frontend presents all information on under-development products and active platform users. These include functionalities like project, team, and document management, functions for user engagement, interactions and activity streams. Furthermore, it guarantees the seamless and integrated access to any third-party services.

The following screenshots showcase indicative instances of the delivered frontends described above.

Figure 2: First Page

Edit Organization Profile

General Facilities Services & Pricing Certifications & Awards

Name Singular Logic **Legal Name** Singular Logic LTD **Legal Form** Limited Company (LTD) ▾

Description

Address

Street Name and Number

Postal Code Postal Code **City** Athens **Country** Greece ▾

P.O. Box P.O. Box **Phone** Phone **Fax Number** Fax Number

Website URL http://... **Instagram** https://www.instagram.com/...

Facebook Page https://www.facebook.com/... **Twitter Account** https://www.twitter.com/...

Cancel Update

Figure 3: Organisation Profile

Email

Password

[Forgot password?](#)

OR

New user? [Register now!](#)

Figure 4: Initial Login Screen

The logo for TOYLABS features a stylized flask with a yellow liquid and a blue gear, with the text 'TOYLABS' in orange and blue.

I agree to the Terms and Conditions

Already have an account? Go to the [Login](#) page.

Figure 5: Initial Registration Screen

The screenshot shows the TOYLABS website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Products' and 'About' tabs, and a user profile for 'Marios Finik'. Below the navigation bar, the 'Products' section is displayed, featuring a search bar and two product cards: 'Toy A Personal' and 'Toy B Singular Logic'. Each product card shows a progress bar with five stages: Concept (Basic Product Information), Research (Market Analysis), Design (Exploring different designs), Prototype (Testing prototypes), and Production (Product is released).

Figure 6: List of Products under Development

The screenshot shows the 'New Product' registration interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the 'TOYLABS' logo, 'Products', and 'About' links. On the right, there are icons for email, notifications (with a '2' badge), and a user profile for 'Marios Finik'. The main content area is titled 'New Product' and is divided into several sections: 'General' (containing 'Title' and 'Description' input fields), 'Category' (a dropdown menu), 'Ages' (a 'Target ages' input field), 'Legal' (with radio buttons for 'Myself' and 'My Organization (Singular Logic)', and a warning icon followed by radio buttons for 'No' and 'Yes'), and 'Images' (a dashed box for file uploads with the text 'Drop files here to upload'). At the bottom right, there are 'Cancel' and 'Create' buttons.

Figure 7: New Product Registration

2.3 Business Layer

2.3.1 TCP Portal Engine

The TCP Portal engine is responsible for implementing all the functions of the TCP. The engine is connected to the frontends of the presentation layer, as well as to the TCP database, where all platform data are stored. It is also connected, through the respective connectors to the ToyLabs added value components, ie. the AR Feedback component, the Market & Trend analysis component and the Partner matching & Negotiation component. The whole operation of the TCP, supporting the workflow of collaboratively developing a new toy is managed by the TCP Portal engine, which however also implements secondary operations which are important for the operation of the platform like user management, communication among users and production of analytics useful both for the users and for the administrators of the platform.

The data that is processed by the TCP Portal engine consists of: data provided by the platform frontends, data generated by specific actions of visitors and users (such as participating in a new product development, responding to requests, providing feedback etc.), data coming from the ToyLabs added value components and, of course, data related to the administration of the system. Based on those data, the TCP Portal engine implements and supports the workflow of collaboratively producing a Toy and collecting feedback throughout the whole process, as described thoroughly in the ToyLabs methodology. Each new product is realized as an extended shared workspace that provides all features to: setup and manage the product development process, collaborate with partners (identified and selected through the Partner Matching and Negotiation component), as well as collect and manage feedback either coming from the partners of each product or from external users and teams. All activities and the actions related to each platform user are captured and analysed, while a complete notification system is also supported providing personalised information, guidance and requests to each user participating in a product development process.

2.3.2 Component Connectors

The Business Layer of the TCP includes the required connectors to the three additional components which are to be developed in ToyLabs. These connectors are responsible for the exchange of all required data among the core platform and the respective components, so that the added value services, although not part of the

TCP, to be integrated in a unified way for the end user. Each connector implements a data processing pipeline allowing the aforementioned seamless integration of the related component to the core platform.

The AR Feedback connector is used in order to retrieve feedback during the design and prototyping phases from user groups called to provide their opinion on toys under development, as well as recommendations for improvement, with the support of AR technology.

The Market & Trends analysis connector is responsible for the communication with the respective component, exchanging the required data for identifying toy industry trends (per toy sector/type) as well as product- and brand- specific feedback based on web and social media analysis.

Finally, the Partner matching & negotiation connector is responsible for exchanging data with the component which handles the operations for identifying the most appropriate partners to collaborate in each product, based on defined criteria, as well as the negotiation process for getting the partners on board.

2.4 Data Layer

2.4.1 TCP Database

The TCP database is the central storage point for all the data that are necessary for the operations of the core platform, including the documents stored and exchanged per product. As such, the component is interconnected with the TCP portal engine which is the only business layer component storing and acquiring data from the database. The connector components of the business layer do not have direct access to the database but only through the TCP Portal engine.

The data stored in the database include among others:

- Login credentials
- Personalized or corporate based user settings
- Users profile data (for all types of users)
- Activity data per user
- Product-related data
- Workflow/ process data per product
- Notifications history
- User Messages
- Exchanged Documents
- Full transaction history
- System log
- etc

All the above-mentioned data is stored in a secure database, and access is provided following specific rules and mechanisms to expose only necessary information.

3 Components Integration Plan

3.1 Releases and Integration Levels

According to Toylabs project deliverable plan, three releases are expected for Toylabs Integrated Platform, described in deliverables D4.2 (first release), D4.3 (second release) and D4.4 (final release), respectively. The integration of the added value components in each release will follow the release of an updated version of each component in the framework of the work performed in WP3.

For each component we distinguish 5 generic integration levels, derived from Eclipse Integration Conformance Levels¹: None, Invocation, Data, API and UI, where:

- None refers to complete lack of integration
- Invocation refers to launching a component as an external process without sharing data or exchanging information
- Data refers to sharing of data in terms of making data manipulated by the platform to be available to the external component and vice versa
- API refers to allowing components to access platform data through tool-specific client APIs
- UI refers to considering component as part of the core platform as if they were designed as a single application. Although this is the highest level of integration of a component to a main platform, this does not require releasing the platform and all components as a single monolithic. Having a user seamlessly move from the core platform to the component and back is what is actually required in this case.

Referring to the Toylabs added-value components, the target is at the final release of the platform to achieve the highest integration level (UI) for all of them. However, in earlier releases of the integrated platform, lower integration levels may also be decided in order to make sure that each component will be fully integrated and thoroughly tested. It is worth noting that in any case, the integration level is also affected by the development status of a given component at each Toylabs Integrated Platform release.

¹ <https://www.eclipse.org/articles/Article-Levels-Of-Integration/levels-of-integration.html>

Out of the three added value components, based on the analysis performed by the technical partners of the consortium, two components (Partner Matching & Negotiation and Market & Trends Analysis) shall be considered crucial for the first release implementation as, based on the ToyLabs methodology, they implement functions supporting the core ToyLabs workflow for collaborative product development, while the third component (Augmented Reality Feedback) refers to a specific part of the process which doesn't interfere with the rest of the workflow.

3.2 Integration Plan

As far as it concerns the releases of the ToyLabs integrated platform, a gradual approach will be followed: first, the integration of the Partner Matching and Negotiation component will take place in order to demonstrate the related feature based on the partner selection methodology. This early integration will prove that a complete process can be executed, including the creation of partners' profiles, the setup of new product development projects, the selection of collaborators and the exchange of documents, messages and notifications. As the component is very close in terms of functions to the core platform operations, the highest integration level (UI) is foreseen even from the 1st release of the integrated platform. The second component to be integrated is the Market & Trends Analysis. As the component is complicated regarding its operation and functions and under constant development, the scope is at the early versions of the integrated platform to achieve API Integration level, so having its own interface. The AR Feedback added-value component will be integrated last, initially at invocation level and then at API level. Complete UI integration of all the components is expected at the third release of the platform.

The schedule of the development circles of the project and the different levels of integration for each component per release of the integrated platform are presented in the following diagram.

Figure 8: Integration Plan Schedule

For the components already integrated in each release, they will be replaced by improved versions developed during each development circle. It is expected that after the first integrated release, the evaluation from the users will provide additional feedbacks which will help in improving the overall system. As already mentioned, further development of the components will also provide additional features to be integrated.

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 At a glance

D4.1 includes a description of the architecture of the ToyLabs Core Platform which has been developed and released by the consortium. The source code is included in the project's GitHub account at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>.

A plan for the integration of the added-value components towards the development of the ToyLabs Integrated Platform has been also provided in the present deliverable, in order to be used as a reference for justifying the exact release times of the components per development circle.

4.2 Next Steps

The next steps include the development of the different added-value components and the preparation for the first release of the ToyLabs Integrated Platform, as presented in the integration plan. Based on the feedback received and any unforeseen issues, the minor amendments to the plan may be decided and – in such case - will be reported accordingly. However, given the progress up to the time the present deliverable is completed, the plan most probably will be followed as-is to the successful completion of the project.

